

A COMPACT AND SCALABLE NEUTRON SPECTROMETER FOR PLANETARY SCIENCE MISSIONS. M. J. Losekamm¹ and S. Paul², ¹European Space Agency, Noordwijk, Netherlands, ²Technical University of Munich, School of Natural Sciences, Garching, Germany; martinjan.losekamm@esa.int.

Introduction: Neutron spectroscopy is by now a well-established tool in planetary science, especially for the detection and quantification of sub-surface water. On airless planetary bodies throughout the solar system, for example, hydrogen-bearing materials like water and hydroxyl-rich compounds can be detected by measuring the relative fluxes of thermal, epithermal, and fast neutrons. These are created by highly energetic (hundreds of MeV and above) cosmic rays and solar particles that can penetrate a planet's surface to depths of several meters. While some of the produced neutrons diffuse upwards through the soil or regolith, they scatter with its constituent nuclei and assume an energy spectrum that is characteristic for its composition [1]. The presence of hydrogen elicits a detectable change in this energy spectrum by lowering the relative flux of epithermal neutrons via moderation. Beyond the search for water, neutron and gamma-ray spectroscopy have become standard techniques for investigating the bulk elemental composition of planetary surfaces, often but not always in combination with active neutron sources [2].

In this contribution, we present the development of a compact scintillator-based neutron spectrometer for planetary science missions that is particularly well suited for applications in the lunar environment.

Instrument Design: We adapted the concept of the Bonner sphere [3] to design a detector that is simple yet robust enough to operate in space or on a planetary surface for prolonged periods of time. Instead of an omnidirectionally sensitive geometry, we implemented a linear one, which allows us to combine the detectors for different neutron energies into one sensor. We could do so based on the assumption that the neutron flux is mostly directional (pointing upwards) with only a narrow angular distribution. We use solid-state thermal-neutron detectors, active moderators, and highly efficient neutron absorbers to construct a detector that can not only detect epithermal and fast neutrons after they were moderated to thermal energies but also measures the energy that they lose in the moderation process. This allows us to perform spectroscopic measurements, a capability that sets our design apart from other, comparable instruments. The whole detector is surrounded by anti-coincidence counters made from plastic scintillators to reliably detect charged cosmic-ray particles and gamma rays that could otherwise lead to erroneous readings. These anti-coincidence counters also allow us to detect neutrons that are scattered out of the central detector stack and exclude them from further analysis.

Our instrument design can easily be adapted to match the sensitivity requirements of different orbital or surface missions, enabling a wide range of possible applications. Though originally developed for the latter, the sensor's simple yet effective design allows us to scale it to sizes suitable for orbital measurements, where count rates are intrinsically lower than on the surface. Adjusting the thickness of the different detector layers allows to fine-tune the energy sensitivity to the range of interest. And deploying an array of identical instruments mounted at different angles on a satellite may also allow recording an angular profile of the neutron flux in orbit.

Capabilities: Using a GEANT4-based simulation, we exemplarily assessed the instrument's ability to detect neutrons and classify them into the three broad energy ranges (thermal: 0.1 eV to 0.4 eV, epithermal 0.4 eV to 0.6 MeV, and fast: 0.6 MeV to 8 MeV) required for the detection of hydrogen. For thermal energies, it can classify more than 98% of detected neutrons correctly; if the detection efficiency is taken into account, almost 90% of incident neutrons are detected and correctly identified. For epithermal energies, the classification is even better at more than 99%, but the combined detection and classification efficiency drops to about 46%. This is expected, as epithermal neutrons have a much lower interaction cross section than thermal ones. The combined efficiency for fast neutrons is slightly better at about 49%, while the classification drops to about 69%, suggesting that the detection efficiency for fast neutrons is larger than for epithermal ones.

In this contribution, we present the overall detector concept and design and how it can be adapted to various mission requirements. We also discuss the performance simulations summarized above.

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